

1 A Novel Microinjection-Based Protocol for Evaluating Gap Junction Dynamics in 3D
2 Multicellular Spheroids

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5 Disclosure statement

6 *The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.*

7 Abstract

8 Background:

9 In-vitro studies have been the centerpiece of most drug and cellular mechanisms studies.
10 Numerous drugs influence various cellular functions, including intercellular communication and
11 signaling; however, the ability to quantify and visually assess these changes has been limited,
12 particularly in advanced in-vitro models such as organoids and spheroids.

13 Objective:

14 To overcome these limitations, we developed a novel microinjection protocol that enables precise
15 dye delivery into individual cells within intact spheroids. This approach allows real-time
16 visualization of gap junctions activity in live cells, providing a more refined and physiologically
17 relevant assessment of intercellular communication. To further enhance the tumor
18 microenvironment model, fibroblasts were incorporated into spheroid co-culture to simulate in-
19 vivo cellular interactions. This protocol enables the analysis of gap junction functionality by
20 measuring dye movement between cells based on the extent of its spread.

21 Methods:

22 For this protocol, fibroblasts were co-cultured with colorectal cancer epithelial cells using
23 CelVivo, Clinostar reactor to generate spheroids exceeding 300 μm in diameter. Microinjection
24 was performed with an Eppendorf Microinjector, delivering a dye mixture of Texas Red and
25 Lucifer Yellow to evaluate gap junction activity.

26 Conclusion:

27 In summary, this protocol presents a novel approach for assessing gap junction activity in 3D
28 spheroids, including co-culture models. It enables the examination of the critical role of gap
29 junctions within complex 3D systems in a unique and physiologically relevant manner.

30 Key Words

31 3D Spheroid, Gap Junction, Microinjection, Cell-Cell Communication, Co-Culture, Colorectal
32 Cancer

33 Introduction:

34 Colorectal cancer continues to be the second most deadly cancer around the world for both men
35 and women with an incidence of close to 150,000 and around 50,000 deaths per year.^{1,2} Despite
36 ongoing research in drug development and treatment, significant gaps and fundamental knowledge
37 remain in the field of colorectal cancer. One key area involves cell-to-cell communication,
38 specifically gap junction-mediated signaling, and how to effectively visualize and analyze the
39 impact of external factor chemicals treatments on this type of communication within 3D models.

40 ³⁻⁶

41 To understand this further, it is essential to consider the molecular basis of gap junctions, formed
42 by channel structures composed of connexin proteins-key components that enable direct
43 intercellular communication.

44 ⁷⁻¹⁰ Six connexins form to make a unit called connexons that vary in structure and combination of
45 each other in different types of tissue and cells. ^{4,11,12} These connexins vary in type and
46 composition across different tissues, contributing to their diverse physiological roles. Abnormal or
47 dysregulated expressions of connexins can disrupt gap junction communication, ultimately
48 contributing to altered cellular growth, differentiation, and tumor progression. ^{7,9,10,13}

49 Previous studies examining connexon expression and alterations have largely relied on 2D
50 monolayer cultures, which fail to accurately mimic *in vivo* conditions. As a result, there has been
51 a growing emphasis on developing *in vitro* models that more closely reflect the physiological
52 environment as *in-vivo*.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ The variability between 2D and 3D cultures comes from the greater
53 complexity of 3D systems and their enhanced ability to interact with both their environments and
54 neighboring cells. ¹⁶⁻¹⁸ These interactions contribute to the resemblance of 3D cultures to *in vivo*
55 conditions, particularly in gene expression, morphology, and signaling pathways.^{19,20} These
56 signaling pathways and gene expression have been illustrated to affect cell-cell communication in
57 3D models, especially in E-cadherin and N-cadherin.

58 In addition to changes in E-cadherin and N-cadherin, gap junction-mediated communication also
59 differs between 2D and 3D models. Significant variations in both expression and functional
60 activity of gap junctions are seen, particularly when organoids are involved. ^{15-17,21-26} One such
61 example is the expression of connexin 43 which regulates anti-apoptotic and proliferative signals
62 while also influencing cancer cell motility which increases metastasis rate.^{10,24,27} Studies have
63 demonstrated connexin 43 expression in certain cancer cell types are drastically different between
64 3D model and 2D models leading to differences in gap junction regulation.²⁴ These changes affect
65 how drugs act on both the cells and the culture system, influencing their potency or lethality.²⁸⁻³¹

66 This highlights the need for reliable model systems and diverse assay approaches to investigate
67 gap junction alterations and interactions.

68 One example of these assays is the Scrape Loading/Dye Transfer assay, which utilizes a
69 small dye (less than 900 Da) that can pass between cells exclusively through intercellular pathways
70 such as gap junctions.³²⁻³⁴ The dye is introduced by mechanically scraping 100% confluent
71 population of attached cells and permits dye entry. After extensive washing, dye is then transferred
72 through the adjacent cells using primary gap junctions. The transfer of dye can then be measured
73 using fluorescent microscopy overtime.³⁴ However, a major limitation of this protocol is its
74 incompatibility with 3D models, as the scraping step required for dye introduction disrupts or
75 damages the spheroids. The key challenge lies in delivering the dye without compromising the
76 structural integrity of the spheroids, making this assay ineffective for use in 3D systems.

77 Additionally, parachute assay is another useful tool to measure functionality of gap
78 junctions.^{35,36} The central concept of this technique involves using dye-preloaded cells that, when
79 co-cultured with unlabeled cells, can transfer the dye through intercellular connections.³⁶ Dye
80 transfer begins once the pre-loaded cells adhere to the monolayer, enabling intercellular
81 interactions that facilitate dye spread.^{35,37} While this technique is well-suited for experiments
82 involving 2D monolayers or 2D co-cultures, it is not a feasible approach for most 3D models. A
83 major challenge lies in integrating the dye-loaded cells into spheroids though possible, the process
84 is inconsistent, and the integration occurs at random locations within the structure.^{25,38} For
85 instance, depending on the method used to generate the spheroid or organoid, the parachuted dye-
86 loaded cells may fail to integrate into the spheroid and instead become trapped in the extracellular
87 matrix between spheroids, rather than being incorporated into the spheroid itself.^{25,38} Similarly, in
88 methods that form 3D models without an extracellular matrix, such as those relying on

89 gravitational forces, dye-loaded cells introduced after spheroid formation may fail to fully
90 integrate.³⁹ Alternatively, if the dye-loaded cells are added during the early stages of spheroid or
91 organoid formation, the dye may become trapped within the spheroid core. This internal
92 localization, combined with dense cell layering, can obstruct fluorescence signals from escaping,
93 limiting the ability to visualize dye transfer.^{6,35,37-39} Therefore, this protocol cannot be reliably
94 used to assess gap junction functionality in 3D models.

95 Lastly, one of the more advanced methods for assessing gap junctions involves the use of
96 quantitative fluorescence resonance energy transfer, commonly known as FRET.^{40,41} This
97 technique is based on the interaction between donor and acceptor fluorophores when they are in
98 close proximity, energy transfer occurs, resulting in light emission that can be quantitatively
99 measured.^{41,42} When applying the FRET method to assess gap junctions, it is typically performed
100 on a limited number of cells. One group of cells is loaded with donor fluorophores, while the other
101 is loaded with acceptor-labeled molecules.⁴⁰⁻⁴³ If these molecules meet in an adjacent cell, a FRET
102 signal is generated, indicating that the molecules have passed through functional gap junctions.
103 There has been limited application of the FRET method in 3D models, and its use still faces notable
104 challenges. One key limitation is uneven distribution of donor and acceptor molecules, where
105 certain regions may receive neither label, resulting in an absence of detectable signal.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶

106 Therefore, there is currently no definitive technique to both visualize and functionally assess gap
107 junction activity to the best of our knowledge. This protocol aims to address this research gap by
108 utilizing microinjection in 3D models. The advantage of using the microinjection protocol over
109 other methods lies in its ability to precisely target a specific region of the spheroid while delivering
110 a controlled dose of dye. Similarly, this technique ensures that the dye remains confined within the
111 cell, preventing external leakage, as it is delivered directly into the cell's interior. Once delivered,

112 the dye will transfer to neighboring cells through intercellular mechanisms. Thus, this protocol
113 will describe and emphasize the use of microinjection as a tool for analyzing gap junctions in 3D
114 models.

115 Materials

- 116 1. Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, Gibco, Cat no. 11966025) cell
117 culture medium: DMEM with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS)
- 118 2. RPMI 1640 (Gibco, Cat no. 31800) cell culture medium: RPMI with 10% fetal
119 bovine serum (FBS)
- 120 3. Incubator set to 37°C, humidity 95 %, CO₂ 5 %.
- 121 4. CelVivo Clinostar incubator (Invitro Technologies)
- 122 5. Nikon Ts2R-FI Inverted Microscope
- 123 6. Eppendorf™ FemtoJet™ 4i Microinjector
- 124 7. Eppendorf TransferMan 4r Micromanipulator
- 125 8. Eppendorf™ Femtotips™ Microinjection Capillary Tips (Eppendorf™, Cat no.
126 E5242957000)
- 127 9. Eppendorf™ Femtotips™ Microloader Tips for Femtojet Microinjector
128 (Eppendorf™, Cat no. 930001007)
- 129 10. Dye solutions: Lucifer Yellow (457.2 Da, green); Texas Red-dextran (10,000 Da,
130 red) did not. Both were 1 mM solutions mixed 1:1 in the Microloader Tips
- 131 11. Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco, Cat no. 15140122)

- 132 12. Caco-2 (ATCC® HTB-37)
- 133 13. T75 (EasYFlask, Thermofisher, Cat no. 156499)
- 134 14. Class II A2 Biological Safety Cabinet
- 135 15. Cell counter
- 136 16. Phosphate buffered saline, pH 7.4 (Gibco, Cat no. 10010023)
- 137 17. Trypsin-EDTA (0.5%), no phenol red
- 138 18. Petri Dishes with Clear Lid (Fisher Scientific, Cat no FB0875714)
- 139 19. Glass Bottom 35mm Cell Culture Dish

140 Methods

141 Establishment of 3D spheroids

- 142 1. Cell growth media for Caco2 with Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM). Add
143 10% Fetal bovine serum and 0.5% penicillin/streptomycin to DMEM media. Grow cells
144 to 80% confluency and prepare 3D CellVivo Culture system.
- 145 2. Prepare the Cellvivo culture by injecting 25 mL of sterile water into the hydration port of
146 the ClinoReactor using a 20-gauge ½-inch needle through the plastic seal, ensuring sterile
147 conditions inside a laminar airflow cabinet. Cover the hole created from the 20- gauge
148 needle with sterilized tape and place the ClinoReactor in a 4°C fridge overnight. After
149 equilibration, wash the front port three times with sterilized PBS and take reactor out of
150 the plastic cover.
- 151 3. Rinse the adherent cells in a T-75 flask three times with PBS. Treat the cells with 3 mL of
152 Trypsin-EDTA (0.5%), no phenol red, to detach them, then pellet the cells by

153 centrifugation. Resuspend the pellet in 5 mL of DMEM containing 10% FBS. Count the
154 cells and seed 5×10^4 cells into the ClinoReactor chamber. Fill the chamber to its
155 maximum capacity with approximately 5 mL of DMEM, ensuring no bubbles are
156 introduced.

157 4. Incubate the ClinoReactor in the Clinostar at 37°C with 5% CO₂ at a rotation speed of 13
158 rpm for one day. This speed keeps the cells suspended in the center of the reactor,
159 promoting spheroid formation. Gradually increase the rotation speed by 0.5 rpm per day
160 to maintain the spheroids in the center. After two weeks, the spheroids will reach an
161 optimal size of 300 microns for microinjections. Additionally, change the media as
162 needed by allowing the spheroids to settle at the bottom of the chamber. Carefully replace
163 the media, ensuring that approximately 200 µL remains to prevent spheroid loss during
164 pipetting.

165 Microinjection of spheroids

166 1. Remove the ClinoReactor from the Clinostar and place it in a sterile laminar flow hood.
167 Carefully open the front port and gently extract the spheroids using wide-bore pipette
168 tips. Transfer all spheroids into a 150 mm petri dish, allowing them to spread out. Select a
169 single spheroid and use a pipette to pass it through a 70 µm cell strainer to remove any
170 small or single cells, handling it carefully to avoid disruption. Place the spheroid in a
171 glass-bottom 35 mm cell culture dish and add 2 mL of DMEM, ensuring the spheroid is
172 positioned at the center of the small chamber within the dish.

173 2. Dip the micropipette into the dye solution of Luciferase Yellow and Texas Red while
174 ensuring the micropipette is not touching any surface or broken. Slowly fill the

175 micropipette with dye without introducing any air bubbles and mount the micropipette to
176 the micromanipulator and angle the micropipette at 33°C from the microscope stage.
177 Ensure the Eppendorf™ FemtoJet™ 4i Microinjector is one and at the lowest injection
178 pressure and compensation pressure. Carefully position the micropipette into the media
179 using the micromanipulator while observing under the microscope.

180 3. Once the micropipette is in the media without touching the surface or any spheroids
181 adjust the compensation pressure to allow consistent leakage of dye from the tip of the
182 micropipette. Increase the injection pressure by 25 psi, adjusting as needed based on the
183 cell type and spheroid thickness. Do not exceed 60 psi, as higher pressure may damage or
184 rupture the cells.

185 4. Carefully maneuver the spheroid to the edge of the 35 mm petri dish, positioning it
186 against the walls of the inner chamber using the micropipette. Be sure not to penetrate the
187 spheroid at this stage. Once the spheroid is positioned against the chamber wall, gently
188 insert the micropipette into the spheroid and inject the dye. The injection should take
189 between 0.5 to 1 second, ensuring the volume is small enough to avoid inducing
190 apoptosis. Make sure there is only one injection point and allow sufficient time before
191 fixing the spheroids to ensure proper time intervals. Once the time intervals are
192 completed proceed to fix and image the spheroid.

193 Fixing and Imaging of Spheroid

194 1. Transfer the spheroid to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf microcentrifuge tube and gently wash it
195 with PBS to remove any residual background dye.

196 2. Cover the Eppendorf tube with foil to protect the dye from light exposure.

- 197 3. Add 1 mL of 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS and incubate for 1 hour.
- 198 4. Wash the spheroids with PBS three times.
- 199 5. Transfer the spheroid to a 35 mm petri dish and prepare it for imaging. Use an excitation
200 wavelength of 485 nm and emission wavelength of 540 nm for Luciferase Yellow, and an
201 excitation wavelength of 580 nm and emission wavelength of 640 nm for Texas Red.
202 Adjust the exposure time and gain settings to capture the best image of the control,
203 maintaining these settings throughout the imaging process.

204 Discussion:

205 This protocol outlines a reliable workflow for generating 3D spheroids, including both
206 monocultures and epithelial–fibroblast co-cultures, with a primary focus on evaluating gap
207 junction dynamics. Using this approach, we established spheroids composed of the fibroblast line
208 CCD-112CoN (CRL-1541) and epithelial cell lines SW620, SW480, Caco-2, and HT-29, either
209 individually or in combination. The use of the 3D CellVivo culture system in combination with
210 Clinoreactor allowed for the controlled spheroid formation under microgravity conditions. This
211 environment minimizes mechanical stress while promoting cell aggregation and tissue like
212 organization, resulting in spheroids with consistent size and morphology. Achieving a target
213 spheroid diameter of approximately 300 μm ensures optimal conditions for microinjection, as
214 larger spheroids may pose increased risk of structural damage during manipulation, while smaller
215 spheroids may lack the complexity required for physiologically relevant modeling. Similarly,
216 smaller spheroids will be difficult to separate from each other while larger spheroids make
217 separation of other spheroids easier.

218 Microinjection of Lucifer Yellow and Texas Red enables precise single cell delivery within
219 the spheroid core, permitting visualization of dye diffusion through intercellular pathways,
220 including gap junctions. This approach provides a direct resolved method to study cell-to-cell
221 communication in a 3D context, overcoming limitations of conventional 2D assays where cell
222 morphology and extracellular matrix interactions differ significantly from in vivo conditions. By
223 controlling injection pressure, compensation pressure, and contact angle, the method minimizes
224 cell damage while ensuring reproducible dye loading.

225 Spheroids were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for one hour, ensuring adequate structural
226 preservation without excessive tissue hardening. Shorter times risk incomplete fixation and dye
227 loss, while longer times may reduce fluorescence intensity and increase autofluorescence, making
228 consistent fixation duration critical for reproducibility. However, fixation time might have to be
229 lessen or increased depending on downstream applications. Histological sectioning of spheroids
230 may require shorter fixation times to prevent excessive tissue hardening. This protocol did not
231 investigate whether the dye remains stable throughout the histology and sample preparation
232 process. All injections in this protocol were performed in glass-bottom 35 mm Petri dishes, which
233 facilitate visualization and maneuvering but also introduce fluid-flow that can displace spheroids
234 during approach. Embedding in thick extracellular matrices such as Matrigel during injection was
235 avoided, as the high viscosity can clog micropipette tips, dampen pressure pulses, and necessitate
236 higher injection pressures that may damage cells. If matrix support is required, a thin surface
237 coating may be preferred and alteration in pressure may be required.

238 Potential sources of technical error include excessive injection pressure, which can rupture
239 cells or disrupt spheroid integrity, and insufficient pressure, which may result in inadequate dye
240 delivery. Continuous dye leakage from the micropipette prior to entry can produce high

241 background fluorescence and lower the signal-to-noise ratio. Mechanical issues such as
242 micropipette tip breakage or passing entirely through the spheroid can lead to structural damage
243 and uneven dye distribution. Air bubbles within the pipette disrupt pressure control, while spheroid
244 drift in the Petri dish can cause missed entry points or shear damage. ECM-related clogging is a
245 particular challenge with viscous environments, and temperature fluctuations can alter dye
246 viscosity and membrane mechanics, affecting ejection consistency. Mitigation strategies include
247 filtering dyes through 0.22 μm membranes, using minimal and incremental pressure adjustments,
248 stabilizing spheroids against the chamber wall, keeping the media depth moderate to reduce drift,
249 and replacing pipettes at the first sign of clogging or damage. Maintaining a bubble-free dye
250 column, avoiding contact with the dish surface during pipette insertion, and pre-testing injection
251 stability before approaching the spheroid are also key steps. Beyond the technical checklist, there
252 are several elements that are difficult to capture in a written protocol but critical to success. These
253 include developing a feel for the subtle resistance change when the micropipette pierces the
254 spheroid, learning to adjust pressures dynamically based on spheroid density and dye viscosity,
255 and recognizing when a spheroid's position or orientation will make injection more prone to
256 damage.

257 The approach has inherent limitations. Microinjection is low throughput and requires specialized
258 equipment and operator training. Single-point injections may underestimate connectivity if the
259 spheroid contains necrotic zones or disconnected cell clusters. The method is also sensitive to
260 biological variables such as spheroid size and extracellular matrix composition. Overall, this
261 method offers a powerful tool for investigating cell-to-cell communication, permeability, and
262 tissue organization in 3D models. It has potential applications in cancer biology, drug delivery

263 studies, and developmental biology, where understanding how molecules move through tissue-like
 264 structures is critical.

265 Table 1:

Issue	Potential Cause	Mitigation Strategy
Cell rupture spheroid disruption	Excessive injection pressure	Apply minimal, incremental pressure adjustments, pre-test injection stability before approaching spheroid.
Inadequate dye delivery	Insufficient pressure; air bubble in pipette	Ensure bubble free dye column adjust pressure gradually back-fill carefully with micro loader.
High background fluorescence	Continuous dye leakage from pipette before entry	Keep needle tip out of media until aligned. replace pipette if leakage occurs; use moderate pressure only after tip is inside cell; wash spheroids at least 3 times with PBS
Structural damage, uneven dye spread	Micropipette tip breakage or passing entirely through spheroid	Avoid over advancing needle; stop at cytoplasm of cells; replace pipette immediately if tip breaks.
Missed entry,	Spheroid drift in dish	Reduce medium depth stabilize spheroid against chamber wall or embed lightly in matrix cushion (last option).
Needle clogging	Extracellular matrix components or viscous environments	Filter dyes through 0.22 μm membranes; replace pipette at first sign of clogging; avoid contact with dish surface. Dilute extracellular matrix
Operator inconsistency	Difficulty detecting subtle resistance change when piercing spheroid, different size spheroid	Practice to develop sensitivity; adjust pressures dynamically based on spheroid density and dye viscosity.
Biological variability	Necrotic zones, spheroid size,	Standardize spheroid preparation (~200–400 μm), avoid injections into necrotic

		cores; use multiple spheroids per condition.
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267 Authors contribution

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269 Conceptualization: Tomas Lugo, Thu Annelise Nguyen

270 Data curation: Tomas Lugo,

271 Formal analysis: Tomas Lugo, Thu Annelise Nguyen

272 Funding acquisition: Thu Annelise Nguyen, Stephanie Myers

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281 Funding details:

282 1. Please supply all details required by your funding and grant-awarding bodies as follows:

283 *For single agency grants*

284 This work was supported by the Harrington Cancer and Health Foundation, Amarillo, TX
 285 and Texas Tech University, School of Veterinary Medicine, Amarillo, TX. We also would
 286 like to acknowledge financial support by Dr. Stephanie Myers.

287 Declaration of interests

288

289 *The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship,*
 290 *and/or publication of this protocol.*

291 Data availability statement

292 *The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this protocol are available*
293 *within the article and its supplementary materials.*

294 Supplemental online material

295 Figures

296

297 *Figure 1: 40x Image of spheroid with micropipette needle and Caco-2 Spheroid*

298

299 *Figure 2: This figure presents an image of the FRTIC filter acquired at 20x magnification*
300 *following the injection procedure.*

301

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303

304

Figure 2: This figure displays a Caco-2 spheroid imaged after a 1-hour incubation period before the washing step.

305

306 *Figure 4: This figure showcases Microinjection system featuring the Eppendorf™*
307 *FemtoJet™ 4i Microinjector, TransferMan 4r Micromanipulator,*

308

309 *Figure 3: This figure represents Spheroids following 14 weeks of growth in the CelVivo Clinostar*
310 *system.*

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